

CONFERENCE ABSTRACT

Molecular characterization of group A rotavirus among hospitalized children in Portugal

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Abstract: About 3 to 5 billion episodes of acute gastroenteritis occur worldwide each year. 75% to 90% of acute gastroenteritis is caused with viruses. Rotavirus is the leading cause of severe childhood gastroenteritis. Children between 6 months and two years are most susceptible to the disease. Confirmed diagnosis of rotavirus gastroenteritis requires testing of fecal specimens. Many times the stool sample test is not performed because it doesn't change the clinical course of gastroenteritis.

Since 2006 two rotavirus vaccines were approved in many countries. European and American clinical trials on two rotavirus vaccines have shown 85-98% efficacy against severe rotavirus gastroenteritis. They also demonstrated that these same vaccines provide a good protection against other strains not included in the vaccine.

According to the literature, five common rotavirus strains (G1P8, G2P4, G3P8, G4P8 and G9P8) were responsible for the most severe rotavirus infections worldwide in the pre-vaccine era and continued predominant in the post-vaccine licensure period.

The aim of the study was to determine the incidence of rotavirus infection and characterize circulating genotypes in children with gastroenteritis hospitalized in a paediatric care unit during the period of 2017 - 2018. A random sample of 47 stool samples were collected and analysed by molecular methods. The diagnose of rotavirus was confirmed in 29 patients aged between 2 months and 6 years and with a predominance of males (n = 18, 62,1%). All children were hospitalized with an average length of hospital stay of five days. In most of the cases it was not possible to establish the source of infection. All patients had diarrhoea and most were associated with vomiting (n = 24, 82,8%). Only four patients were vaccinated against rotavirus, and one had incomplete vaccination. In the sample analysed the most common strains was G3P8 (n=13, 44,8%) followed by G1P8 (n=8, 27,6%), G9P8 (n=5, 17,2%), G4P8 (n=2, 6,9%) and G3P9 (n=1, 3,5%)

Despite the limitations inherent to the study (small and random sample, study carried out in a single institution), it can be concluded that almost all acute gastroenteritis to rotavirus are secondary to the five common rotavirus strains. Introducing the vaccine into the national vaccination program could be beneficial. However, the possible change in the prevalence of rotavirus strains and emergence of the new strains after vaccination should be considered.

Keywords: Rotavirus, vaccines, children, strains.

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